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Influence of Social Media on Reading Habits and Performance in Social Studies among Upper Basic School students in Delta State

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Abstract

This research investigated the influence of social media on reading habits and performance in Social Studies among Upper Basic School students in Delta State, Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. A well-structured questionnaire titled ‘Social Media Influence on Reading Habits and Performance Questionnaire’ (SMIRHAPQ) was used as the instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was validated by two (2) experts in educational research and (2) two lecturers in the department of Social Science Education Delta State University, Abraka and had a reliability coefficient of 0.85, established through a pilot test using the Cronbach Alpha method. The population of the study consisted of 1,094 Upper Basic Class two (2) Social Studies students (444 males and 650 females) during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State, Nigeria. A multi-stage sampling technique was employed to select a representative sample of 300 students (120 males and 180 females) drawn from the three senatorial districts of the State. Data collected were analyzed using Chi-square and t-test statistical methods. The findings revealed that there is a significant influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in upper basic schools. Additionally, it was found that social media usage significantly influences students’ performance in Social Studies. However, there was no significant difference in the performance of Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not in upper basic schools in Delta State. The study concluded that while social media has both positive and negative impacts, its potential for enhancing educational outcomes cannot be ignored if effectively managed. It recommended that schools, educators, parents, and policymakers should collaboratively promote responsible social media use through education, curriculum integration, parental guidance, and engaging classroom activities to enhance academic focus and leverage its potential for learning

Keyword: Social Media Usage, Reading Habits, Performance, Social Studies, Upper Basic school students.

Introduction

The rapid proliferation of social media platforms has significantly transformed communication, education, and information dissemination in the 21st century. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, WhatsApp, and X (formerly Twitter) dominate daily interactions, reshaping how individuals connect, learn, and share information. For students, these platforms serve dual purposes: as sources of entertainment and as tools for educational exploration. However, this digital shift presents a paradox, with both positive and negative implications for academic performance and traditional reading habits (Musa & Emmanuel, 2017). In the educational domain, social media seems to democratize access to knowledge, fostering collaborative learning through interactive groups, tutorials, and discussion forums. Social media provides opportunities for engaging with diverse content, expanding global awareness, and promoting participatory learning experiences. Yet, the overwhelming influx of information and the addictive design of these platforms raise significant concerns about their impact on students’ focus, time management, and cognitive abilities (Hou & Xu, 2024). In subjects like Social Studies, which emphasize critical reading, analytical thinking, and the exploration of societal dynamics, the effects of social media usage may be particularly notable. The emergence of digital distractions may often shift students’ attention from in-depth reading to superficial engagement with fragmented content. Consequently, there is a growing apprehension about the erosion of reading habits and its potential consequences on academic performance, particularly for upper basic education students in Delta State,

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Nigeria. Reading has long appeared to have been regarded as the cornerstone of academic success and intellectual development. Traditional reading practices, involving printed materials such as textbooks, newspapers, and academic journals, may provide students with structured and immersive learning experiences. Scholars like Paige et.al (2024) underscored the role of sustained and focused reading in enhancing comprehension, critical thinking, and overall academic performance. Through traditional reading, learners may develop an understanding of complex concepts and are better equipped to engage with academic materials critically. Additionally, reading seems to foster cognitive skills such as memory retention, vocabulary acquisition, and analytical reasoning. Le et.al (2024) stated that exposure to extensive reading positively influences vocabulary growth and comprehension, creating a strong foundation for learning across disciplines. For subjects like Social Studies, which require understanding nuanced societal concepts and historical contexts, traditional reading may appear indispensable.

The influence of traditional reading habits extends beyond academic success to include broader societal impacts. Studies by Osharive (2015) stated that regular reading habits contribute to better communication skills and social awareness, which are essential for shaping informed and responsible citizens. Social Studies, as a discipline, is closely aligned with these objectives, as it aims to inculcate civic competence and ethical reasoning among students. In the 21st century, the rapid growth of social media platforms has redefined the way individuals consume information. Platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and WhatsApp have introduced new modes of communication, enabling users to share content instantly and engage in discussions globally. While these platforms offer unprecedented opportunities for knowledge exchange, their impact on traditional reading habits and educational outcomes has been a subject of scholarly concern.

Social media may encourage a culture of rapid information consumption, where users interact with fragmented and brief content rather than engaging deeply with extended texts. Musa (2017) notes that the over-reliance on social media for information can undermine the skills required for critical reading and analytical thinking. This shift poses a significant challenge to students' academic performance, particularly in subjects like Social Studies, which demand a deep engagement with texts and critical evaluation of ideas. Moreover, the addictive nature of social media platforms has raised concerns about their effects on students' time management and focus. In the views of Adekunjo et.al (2024) excessive use of social media often leads to procrastination and reduced academic productivity. In Delta State, where educational resources are already stretched, the increasing dependence on social media seems to add a layer of complexity to efforts aimed at maintaining high academic standards.

The educational systems may face unique challenges in balancing technological advancements with traditional learning goals. Limited access to infrastructure, insufficient training for teachers, and a lack of awareness about effective technology integration tend to exacerbate the issues caused by social media usage. For instance, Almusaed et.al (2023) emphasizes that while technology can enhance learning, its misuse often leads to a decline in students' academic engagement and performance. Social Studies as a subject is particularly vulnerable to these challenges. As a discipline that aims to promote critical thinking and civic engagement, it relies heavily on students' ability to comprehend and analyze complex texts. The prevalence of superficial reading habits fostered by social media use may undermine these objectives, making it difficult for educators to achieve desired learning outcomes.

In addition, economic disparities within Delta State mean that not all students have equal access to digital tools or printed materials. According to Peras et.al (2023) socioeconomic factors play a significant role in determining students' reading habits and academic success. This digital divide may further complicate efforts to integrate technology into education without compromising traditional learning practices. Several studies have explored the interplay between reading habits and social media usage, offering insights into the challenges and opportunities presented by this digital shift. Sivakumar et.al (2023) revealed that social media can promote knowledge sharing and can increase student motivation and performance. The findings suggested that social networking is a valuable method of information dissemination and can be used to encourage student engagement. Furthermore, Javeed (2023) revealed a positive correlation between excessive social media use and academic performance. The findings are consistent with observations where students who spend more time on social media platforms tend to perform excellently in subjects requiring sustained reading and analytical skills.

In the same vein, other scholars argued that social media can be harnessed to complement traditional reading practices. For instance, Mosharrafa et.al (2024) opined that integrating social media into classroom activities can enhance students' engagement and motivation. By encouraging discussions and collaborative projects, educators can use these platforms to create dynamic learning environments that align with the objectives of Social Studies education. Musa and Emmanuel (2017) examined how social media influences the reading culture of students at Kaduna Polytechnic, finding that excessive time spent on social media negatively impacts academic reading and performance. They recommended integrating social media into the curriculum and improving library facilities to support effective learning. Osharive (2015) investigated the impact of social

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media on the academic performance of undergraduate students, revealing significant addiction and recommending its use for educational purposes while emphasizing parental and teacher monitoring to balance academic and social media activities. Suci et.al (2022) reviewed literature from 2015 to 2020 by highlighting the role of social media in facilitating collaborative and interactive online learning, especially during pandemic-induced school closures. Findings emphasized that while social media promotes resource. Ansari et.al (2020) examined the role of social media and mobile devices in collaborative learning, revealing their significant impact on interactivity with peers, teachers, and knowledge sharing, which enhances students' engagement and academic performance. Using a structural equation model, data from 360 students in eastern India highlights how social media fosters creativity, dynamism, and a research-oriented mindset among learners. The findings are that sharing, interaction, and collaboration, effective planning and management are crucial to optimizing its educational potential.

Achieving a balance between technology integration and traditional learning is crucial for addressing the challenges posed by social media usage. Strategies such as digital literacy training, time management workshops, and the promotion of reading culture could help mitigate the adverse effects of social media on students' academic performance. Digital literacy programmes, for example, can equip students with the skills needed to navigate online platforms responsibly and critically. By teaching students how to discern credible sources and evaluate information critically, educators can foster habits that support academic success (Erwin and Mohammed, 2022). Similarly, time management workshops could help students prioritize their academic responsibilities and minimize distractions caused by social media. Promoting a culture of reading is undoubtedly important. Initiatives such as book clubs, reading competitions, and the incorporation of engaging texts into the curriculum may encourage students to develop sustained reading habits. For Social Studies, incorporating real-world case studies and multimedia resources could make traditional reading materials more appealing and relevant to students.

Statement of the Research Problem:

The rapid proliferation of social media platforms has reshaped how students interact, learn, and engage with information. While these platforms offer significant educational opportunities, such as collaborative learning and access to diverse content, their pervasive use also raises concerns about their impact on students' academic performance and traditional reading habits. Social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, WhatsApp, and X (formerly twitter) may often divert students' attention from structured, immersive reading to fragmented and superficial consumption of information. In Social Studies, a subject that demands critical reading, analytical thinking, and the ability to interpret complex societal dynamics, this shift could pose unique challenges. The potential erosion of traditional reading habits associated with focus, comprehension, and deep learning may hinder students' ability to grasp core Social Studies concepts effectively. This issue is particularly critical for upper basic education students in Delta State, Nigeria, where the integration of traditional reading practices with digital tools is essential for achieving educational outcomes.

Despite the recognized benefits of traditional reading in fostering cognitive skills, such as memory retention, vocabulary growth, and critical reasoning, the addictive and time-consuming nature of social media use threatens these gains. Previous studies have established a correlation between sustained reading and academic excellence; however, limited research has explored how social media influences students' reading habits and their subsequent performance in Social Studies. This study, therefore, seeks to address the pressing question: How does social media use affect reading habits and academic performance among Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State?

Objectives of the study

1. Examine the influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State.
2. determine the influence of social media usage on performance in Social Studies among Upper Basic schools students in Delta State.
3. determine the mean performance score of students taught Social Studies using social media and those not exposed to social media in Upper Basic schools in Delta State.

Research Questions

1. How does social media usage influence the reading habits of Social Studies students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State?
2. How does social media usage influence academic performance in Social Studies among students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State?
3. What is the mean performance score of students taught Social Studies using social media compared to those not exposed to social media in Upper Basic schools in Delta State?

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Hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State.
2. There is no significant influence of social media usage on academic performance in Social Studies among students in Upper Basic schools in Delta State.
3. There is no significant difference in the performance of Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not in Upper Basic schools in Delta State.

Methodology

This research investigated the influence of social media on reading habits and performance in Social Studies among Upper Basic School students in Delta State, Nigeria. The study employed a descriptive survey research design, utilizing a well-structured questionnaire titled "Social Media Influence on Reading Habits and Performance Questionnaire" (SMIRHAPQ) for data collection. The instrument comprised two sections: the first gathered demographic information about the respondents, while the second included items on social media usage and its effects on reading habits and academic performance, with response options ranging from Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree. The questionnaire was validated by two experts in educational research and two lecturers from the Department of Social Science Education, Delta State University, Abraka. Reliability was established through a pilot test conducted using the Cronbach Alpha method, which yielded a coefficient of 0.85, indicating high reliability. The study population consisted of 1,094 Upper Basic Class Two (JSS 2) Social Studies students, comprising 444 males and 650 females, enrolled during the 2023/2024 academic session in Delta State. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select a representative sample of 300 students, including 120 males and 180 females, drawn from the three senatorial districts of the state. Data collection involved the administration of all 300 questionnaires, which were retrieved immediately by the researcher to ensure completeness. The data were analyzed using Chi-square and t-test statistical methods.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis 1:

There is no significant influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Table 1: Chi-square Analysis for the influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Variables	N	Df Ls	Crit X2 value	Calc X2 value	decision	
Social Media usage	324	2	0.05	5.991	132.074	Rejected

Reading habits

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The results in Table 1 indicate that the calculated Chi-square value of 132.074 is significantly higher than the critical Chi-square value of 5.991 at a 0.05 level of significance with 2 degrees of freedom. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State. This implies that social media usage significantly influences the reading habits of these students.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant influence of social media usage on academic performance in Social Studies among students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Table 2: Chi-square Analysis for the influence of social media usage on academic performance in Social Studies among students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Variables	N	Df Ls	Crit X2 value	Calc X2 value	Decision
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social media	324	2 0.05	5.991	47.501	Rejected
academic performance					

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The results in Table 2 show that the calculated Chi-square value of 47.501 is significantly greater than the critical Chi-square value of 5.991 at a 0.05 level of significance with 2 degrees of freedom. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which posits that social media usage does not significantly influence academic performance in Social Studies among students, is rejected. This implies that social media usage has a significant influence on students' academic performance in Social Studies.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Table 3: t-test comparison of academic performance of Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not in upper basic schools in Delta State

Source of variation	N	\bar{x}	SD	DF	T	P value
Students who do not use Social media frequently	14	188.64	14.789			
Students who use social Media frequently	164	129.31	21.802	176	1.569	0.118

Source: Author's Survey, 2024

The results in Table 3 indicate a comparison of academic performance between Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not. The mean score (\bar{x}) for students who do not frequently use social media is 188.64, with a standard deviation (SD) of 14.789, while the mean score for students who frequently use social media is 129.31, with a standard deviation of 21.802. The t-test value is 1.569 with a P-value of 0.118. Since the p-value (0.118) is greater than the significance level of 0.05, the difference in academic performance between the two groups is not statistically significant. This implies that frequent use of social media does not have a significant impact on the academic performance of Social Studies students in upper basic schools in Delta State.

Discussion of Findings

The Chi-square analysis in Table 1 indicates a significant influence of social media usage on the reading habits of Social Studies students in Upper basic schools in Delta State ($\chi^2 = 132.074$), ($p < 0.05$). This finding suggests that social media usage plays a critical role in shaping students' reading habits, potentially affecting their focus and engagement with academic materials. This finding agrees with Liu et.al (2023) who found that excessive use of social media platforms like Facebook reduces time spent on academic reading and can negatively impact reading efficiency and comprehension. Corroborating this view Benaicha and Benghalem (2024) reported that students who frequently use social media tend to allocate less time to academic activities, including reading, thereby diminishing their academic engagement. These results align with the hypothesis that social media introduces distractions that disrupt reading routines and time management, underscoring the importance of balanced media use among students.

The Chi-square analysis in Table 2 also reveals a significant influence of social media usage on academic performance in Social Studies ($\chi^2 = 46.500$), ($p < 0.05$). This suggests that the way students engage with social media affects their academic outcomes. This finding is supported by Sun and Chao (2024) who opined that the pervasive use of social media contributes to reduced concentration and academic achievement due to multitasking and decreased study time. This aligned with the view of Nabung (2024) who observed that while social media can facilitate learning through information sharing, excessive use often hinders academic performance by diverting attention from educational goals. The findings emphasized that while social media can be a useful educational tool, unregulated usage may adversely affect academic success, necessitating awareness programmes to promote its responsible use.

The t-test analysis shows no statistically significant difference in the academic performance of Social Studies students who frequently use social media and those who do not ($t = 1.569$), ($p > 0.05$). The mean score of students who do not use social

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media frequently (188.64) is higher than those who do (129.31), but the difference is not enough to establish significance. This finding contradicts the views of Adeleke et.al (2024) who argued that while frequent social media use correlates with lower academic performance, other factors such as individual study habits and time management also play a critical role. They believed that students who do not use social media would perform better. Musa and Emmanuel (2017) noted that the relationship between social media and academic outcomes is nuanced, with potential benefits for students who use it for educational purposes but risks for those who primarily use it for entertainment while students who read through traditional means may also underperform due lack of focus.

Conclusion

The study reveals that social media usage significantly influences the reading habits of Social Studies students in Delta State, with excessive use leading to reduced engagement with academic materials. This finding underscores the importance of maintaining a balance in media use to preserve effective reading habits. Additionally, social media usage significantly impacts students' academic outcomes, highlighting its dual potential for educational engagement and hindrance to concentration and performance when unregulated. However, the analysis found no statistically significant difference in academic performance between frequent and infrequent users, suggesting that other factors, such as study habits and time management, play a more critical role.

Recommendations

1. Schools and educators should organize workshops and campaigns to educate students about the positive and negative impacts of social media on their academic life.
2. School authorities should include modules in the curriculum that teach students how to balance social media use with academic responsibilities effectively.
3. Parents should monitor and regulate their children's social media usage to minimize distractions and enhance their focus on academic activities.
4. Encourage the use of social media as a learning tool for collaborative activities, resource sharing, and educational content.
5. Schools should establish guidelines for the responsible use of social media, emphasizing its integration into academic purposes without compromising focus. Teachers should design engaging activities that compete with social media distractions, such as interactive lessons and group discussions.

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References

- Adekunjo, O. & Unuabor, S. (2024). Effect of Social Media on the Reading Culture of Selected Private Secondary School Students in Akinyele Local Government Area, Ibadan, Oyo State Nigeria. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 10, 15-31.
- Adeleke, I. A., Owolabi, H. L., & Muraina, I. O. (2024). Social Media Usage and English Language Performance of Secondary Students in Ilorin, Kwara State. *Faculty of Natural and Applied Sciences Journal of Computing and Applications*, 2(1), 15-23.
- Almusaed, A., Almssad, A., Yitmen, I., & Homod, R. Z. (2023). Enhancing Student Engagement: Harnessing AIED's Power in Hybrid Education-A Review Analysis. *Education Sciences*, 13(7), 632
- Ansari, J. A. N., Khan, N. A. (2020). Exploring the Role of Social Media in Collaborative Learning the New Domain of Learning. *Smart Learn. Environ.* 7, 9 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40561-020-00118-7>

Influence of Social Media ... (Onyekpe & Ossai, 2024) DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15079855>

- Benaicha, B., & Benghalem, B. (2024). Exploring the Impact of Social Media on EFL Reading Preferences and Habits. *Asian Journal of English Language Studies (AJELS)*, 12(1), 111.
- Erwin, K., & Mohammed, S. (2022). Digital literacy skills instruction and increased skills proficiency. *International Journal of Technology in Education and Science (IJTES)*, 6(2), 323-332. <https://doi.org/10.46328/ijtes.364>
- Hou, Y., Qin, C., & Xu, P. (2024). Social Media Use and Academic Performance in Chinese Children and Adolescents: A Moderated Chain Mediation Model. *Behavioral Sciences*, 14(10), 867.
- Javeed, Aiman. (2023). Impact of Using Social Media on the Academic Performance A Case of College Going Students in Loralai Division. *Siazga Research Journal*. 2. 10.58341/srj.v2i1.12.
- Le, H. V., Nguyen, T. A. D., Le, D. H. N., Nguyen, P. U., & Nguyen, T. T. A. (2024). Unveiling Critical Reading Strategies and Challenges: A Mixed-Methods Study among English Major Students in a Vietnamese higher Education Institution. *Cogent Education*, 11(1), 2326732.
- Liu, Z., Hu, R., & Bi, X. (2023). The effects of social media addiction on reading practice: a survey of undergraduate students in China. *Journal of Documentation*, 79(3), 670-682
- Mosharrafa, R. A., Akther, T., & Siddique, F. K. (2024). Impact of Social Media Usage on Academic Performance of University Students: Mediating role of mental health under a cross-sectional study in Bangladesh. *Health science reports*, 7(1) <https://doi.org/10.1002/hsr2.1788>
- Musa, A. S., & Emmanuel, A. A. (2017). Influence of the social media on the reading culture of Nigerian students: a study of students in Kaduna Polytechnic. *Issues in language and literary studies*, 1(2).
- Nabung, A. (2024). Exploring the Impact of Culture Shock among Tertiary EFL Learners in Indonesia. *Asian Journal of Language, Literature and Culture Studies*, 7(2), 240-250.
- Osharive, P. (2015). Social media and academic performance of students in University of Lagos Undergraduate research Project, University of Lagos.
- Paige, D., & Rupley, W., & Ziglari, L (2024). Critical Thinking in Reading Comprehension: Fine Tuning the Simple View of Reading. *Education Sciences*. 14. 10.3390/educsci14030225.
- Peras, I., Klemenčič M. E., Japelj P. B., & Mekiš R. Ž (2023). Digital versus Paper Reading: A Systematic Literature Review on Contemporary Gaps according to Gender, Socioeconomic Status, and Rurality. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 13(10), 1986-2005.
- Sivakumar, A., Jayasingh, S., & Shaik, S. (2023). Social Media Influence on Students' Knowledge Sharing and Learning: An Empirical Study. *Education Sciences*. 13, 745.
- Suci, W., Muslim, S., & Chaeruman, U. A. (2022). Use of Social Media for Collaborative Learning in Online Learning: A literature review. *AL-ISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 14(3), 3075–3086.
- Sun, W., & Chao, M. (2024). Exploring the influence of excessive social media use on academic performance through media multitasking and attention problems: a three-dimension usage perspective. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1-23